

Implementation of strategies for monitoring and control of professional practices in a higher educational institution of tourism studies (CUCEA)

Dr: Arturo Laure Vidriales¹
Master. Jaime Grover Vaca²

Institutional affiliation: University of Guadalajara, Mexico.

Abstract:

All organizations and institutions, when they are established, they usually start with its fiscal and legal creation, which is what can be considered its base form, it is also important to consider the social aspect, starting with well-organized people and which is the reason for being part of the organization: this is a common objective, a better place to live.

One of the areas that is important to get involved with other organizations or companies are the public relations, in this paper would be focused in an educational institution in order to coordinated set actions and strategic communication, and whose main objective is to strengthen links with various organizations and people; in this interactive practice they should listen, inform and persuade them to achieve consensus, support actions in the present and future to form good students and better human beings.

Professional Practice in the educational area are activities that allows students to develop skills, attitudes, values, and apply the knowledge and abilities acquired in the classroom, these skills are share through their participation in the social, public or private area.

At the university of Guadalajara, has encouraged all head of departments in the campus to make sure to form students in a integrally form, it means not only with sufficient theories but also enough hours practice.

Key words:

Professional practices, integral formation, curricula and supervising.

Fundamentention:

Professional Practice in a educational institution is the training activity during their staying at an educational institution that allows students to develop skills, attitudes, values, and application of knowledge acquired in the classroom, through their participation in the social, public or private area, that are temporary and obligatory for students to get the Degree in Tourism by (CUCEA).¹

Practices provide opportunities for students, since they allow them to gain experience in the workplace, creating a network of contacts, and apply their knowledge. On the other hand, these help companies identify practitioners who are likely to be hired.

In addition to these, in the Department of Tourism, Recreation and Service at CUCEA has determined to initiate a process of linking with various productive sectors and the public

¹ Economic and Administrative Sciences Campus, this is one of the 15 campuses that are run by the University of Guadalajara

and social areas in order to increase the offer for the development of professional practices in its various forms, all of the in concordance with CONAET.²

The curriculum of the Bachelor of Tourism by CUCEA has been updated in 2012, based on the recommendations of the CIEES,³ in this case CONAET, in training areas and fields that evaluates the overall CENEVAL⁴ a last stage exam in Bachelor of Tourism EGEL-T and the needs of the labor market that allows the upgrade fulfillment of the mission of the University of Guadalajara (U de G), and Tourism Program (TP) in the sense of creating, transmit, expand and disseminate knowledge in order to be comprehensively competitive professionals, critics and analysts, committed to society, towards internationalization, contributing to the development of the tourism industry through research and by supporting an educational model of excellence that allow them to be able to identify opportunities and propose solutions to the social, economic and cultural environment.

The Review Committee and redesign curricula of Tourism Program, in which a teacher was involved in a process of decision making in this area from five Academies Tourism Program, the Program Coordinator and the Head of Department, joined this activity. That committee held several working meetings to analyze the Curriculum, based on the recommendations of the CIEES, training areas and fields that evaluate CENEVAL the General Termination Exam of the Bachelor of Tourism and EGEL-T that labor market needs.

Objectives:

General:

Put into action strategies in order to fulfill the institutional requirements in the area of professional practices in the program of Bachelor in Tourism at CUCEA.

Particular:

Make teachers be part of the solution by monitoring the professional practices integral form.

Analyze the areas that CONAET requires for professional practice in order to fulfill the request to be a creditable program.

Updating the curriculum:

The total credits that the student must covered according to the program from 433 credits was reduced to 426 credits, this means less hours in front of the group and more hours of practice in related areas of the tourism industry.

In August 2012, it entered into force the new curriculum, the same that was updated with an integrated approach, covering all functional areas of tourist establishments, with emphasis on be in permanent touch with the productive sector.

² CONAET is the National Council for Quality Tourism Education, an organization that evaluates and gives accreditation to institutions that have tourism studies in their curriculum.

³ CIEES is an organization devoted to the evaluation of Higher Education in Mexico. It is the largest body for quality assurance in higher education in Mexico.

⁴ General evaluation office

Table 1. New curriculum for Bachelor in Tourism at CUCEA

Formation areas	Credits required	%
Common area Obligatory Basic Training	102	24%
Particular area Obligatory Basic Training	178	42%
Particular area Selective Basic Training	24	6%
Mandatory Training Area Specialized	70	16%
Selective Training Area Especialized	24	6%
Area Elective Training Open	28	6%
Number of credits required in order to get the degree	426	100%
Source: http://www.cucea.udg.mx/carreras?q=vida-academica/carreras/turismo/nuevo-plan-estudios-tur		

In October 2012 the Departmental Association endorsed the obligation of professional practices as a subject in the new curriculum, which would take effect in the cycle 2013-A. (February 2013), Each curriculum of the new one has an specific practical training to determine paragraph and programs from the old plan has also been updated in this area. Therefore, in late 2013-B calendar, the Departmental body authorized the design of a new strategic program of practices in all its forms, with an emphasis on specialization, which is presented in this document.

There are lines of materials that are not immediately subsequent to be able to do internships between them, in order to achieve a better theoretical and practical training back to the theory.

Thus, the practical component is present in the three career levels, beginner, intermediate and advanced, in order for students to contrast the theory with direct application, through different modalities. Practical training is fundamental in tourism education, especially higher level. CONAET meet the recommendations of professional practices will be conducted with a total of 450 hours, divided as follows:

Types of practices according to CONAET

1) Induction: they are a group and educational visits, either to the tourist facilities, government sector, and / or sites of heritage value. For these practices it should be specified the learning objectives and a work plan shall be considered optional. Students who cannot cover expenses or don't have enough time to fulfill the requirement; they must carry out other activities that cover the same objectives that are established in the program.

2) Approach: are individual or group visits to perform basic research in order to identify the application of theory in the operation of the tourism area or discipline in various subjects of the curriculum (whether or not discipline, for example: applied accounting, statistics, marketing, etc.) as well as the characteristics of the discipline.

3) Simulation: Use laboratories and / or workshops on campus or check with evidence that has linkage agreements to use other facilities in areas such as food and beverage, computer specialist in the planning, operation and management of tourism, business roundtables, etc.

4) Professionalization: make the student staying in the tourism sector of the discipline of Educational Program as a partner, programmed, operated and evaluated under the supervision of the institution, according to ending program profile. The ideal is to go from the general to the particular, from the operative to the expert, carried out during holiday periods beginning on preference and the first cycles of the curriculum.

NOTE: The type of practice was taken of the assessment document and practices of the University of Colima presented to CONAET and approval, objectives and methods of implementation, monitoring and follow-up depends on the Departmental School.

Table 2. Proposal of types of practices and their variables.

Modality	Characteristics	Obligatoriness
Induction	They are held in the first semesters of the degree, within subjects offered in blocks of the curriculum of the Bachelor of Tourism, by conducting visits to tourist destinations in the region and companies. They can impact various subjects, not just one. They should end up in a product. Total 50 hours	Trips: extracurricular; may not as a must. Visits in the same town: co-curricular.
Approach	It works with different subjects within the subjects offered in blocks of Curriculum of the Bachelor of Tourism, as sustainable tourism, administration, tourism marketing, among others, through links with companies in which students participate the nature of the activity. Total 50 hours	Curricular
Simulation	Use of laboratories and/or workshops on campus, or in other facilities by invitation, as practice time in different subjects. Total 50 hours	Curricular
Professionalization	In-situ of insertion in the labor-professional with credits given (new curriculum) or as a requirement of graduation. ⁵ They can be made at three levels: operational (the first cycles), middle management (mid-career), and management or planning (at the end of the race). Total 300 hours	Curricular

Source: own elaboration with information of teacher Angelica Guerra

They defined four modalities or types of practice, which together constitute the basic framework for the training of students, besides the theoretical component.

In order to do this as a process of socialization and information about the modalities of practices, in the same New Plan of the Bachelor of Tourism CUCEA, it was agreed that the subject "Professional Practice degree in tourism" is taught, inserted in the Training Compulsory Especializante the same plan, giving 8 credits.

In order to evaluate and measure the professional practices in the Bachelor of Tourism CUCEA intended to define the internship program different times formalization and systematization operation thereof. It stresses the need for agreements with tourist organizations for the different levels of practice. Currently, there are agreements with companies in major tourist destinations in the country, ranging from hotels, restaurants, alternative tourism companies, travel agencies, event management companies and banquets, airlines, airports, corporate hotels and international recognition thematic parks. The agreements specify who will be the coordinator of professional staying, who is responsible for allocating student tutors for each destination.

Some of the criteria that qualify are: responsibility, punctuality, spirit of service, cooperation, teamwork, and initiative, among others.

For these propose are included two main destinations in the state, which are the metropolitan area of Guadalajara and Puerto Vallarta for operational practices, which are nearby destinations.

For middle management practices, it is done the same way as operational practices; he/she would have a tutor and monitoring is done similarly, the tutor makes an in-situ monitoring and has an interview with the area supervisor and together fill a qualification and evaluation forms.

Upon completion of the various levels of practice students must submit a report in which a case where the student makes a proposal to improve the company they are staying at, specifically in the department where he/she was giving practices. It also gives a number of documents showing the process of practices such acceptance letter, letter of termination and tutors, delivered to the coordination of practical evaluation reports, which are answered in conjunction with the company supervisors.

Table No. 3 Cycle monitoring practices

Source: Own elaboration.

Table 3 shows the stages of supervision of students participating in the professional practices of the Bachelor of Tourism CUCEA.

General provisions and penalties

Students have an optional insurance by national social security, this is the given by the University of Guadalajara, all students of the University have this benefit, before going to his first practice, when he/she is out of state, students make valid their rights and with this they can use social security facilities anywhere in the country.

The participation of the tutor in the process of monitoring and evaluation of Professional Practice

There is a coordinator in charge of operating the Internship Program of Bachelor of Tourism, at the beginning of each semester students must select the destination and type of corporate in which they wish to do their internship specialization together with the coordinator of practices according to the offer, such coordination is guided and informed of all the agreements and the positions available for a specific holiday period, thus, the Head of Department program assigns a teacher-tutor to each student generally a guardian is appointed by destination, and thus resources, the assigned tutor, visit their mentees and has an interview with Human Resources managers and in some cases even with supervisors.

One of the requirements for Accreditation of professional practice, according to the rules of professional practice, is reporting or memory with the figure proposed university-company following the guidelines Coordination of Professional Practice issued. These, they should mention students in memory include detailed description of the activities during practice and also present their findings, where students offer solutions for improving business processes. There are evaluation forms where teachers, tutors together with supervisors of enterprises qualifying students in several categories, from punctuality, responsibility to the spirit of service, among others, note that the tutor and the supervisor are always in constant communication and any problems would be easily solved at any time let alone our students, and they know they have the unconditional support of his tutor when required.

On the other hand, there are agreements with a large number of tourism businesses, such as hotels, restaurants and bars, airport, travel agencies, alternative tourism companies, tour operators, government agencies, theme parks, companies organization events, boutique hotels, among others, the agreement mentions the different types of practices that students can do in different companies, as well as the number of hours, and what they are entitled and which are creditors. The company will give the student at the end of their internship, a certificate attesting term where it successfully completed their probationary period. The Coordinator of this area ensures that no student is to be a company without having signed a cooperation agreement. Where, schedules, jobs, rest days, number of hours worked, managing holidays, food, transportation, uniforms, etc. specified The agreement will be concluded in writing, to which they are entitled and which they are not entitled students. At the end of the internship is always a result of the efficiency of the student will, because we have teachers-tutors who make such supervision.

Table 3 Obligations of each of the actors of the Professional Practices in monitoring and control.

Position	Obligation	Strategietofulfill	Result
Head of the Department	Assign the minimum workload hours to tutor-teacher	Manage this with the relevant authorities to make it effective	Give the conditions for the Professional Practices are successful
Internships Coordinator	Expand existing agreements in order to offer variety of spaces to make it accessible.	She will visit areas of the tourism industry in order to expand existing agreements.	Offer more choice for an activity related to several sectors.
Professor	Monitor the students assigned to the three stages of the PP, including three visits to the space allocated to practitioners, meet with the manager and make him to evaluate his/her performance of the practitioner.	It will be assigned the minimum load of hours for teaching for the purpose of the (maximum-Minimal) remaining hours would be applied to this activity.	comprehensive evaluation

Source: own elaboration

Conclusions:

All internship programs should be governed by rules, formats for reports of practical, personal files, evaluation form, etc. standards and specifications that will meet both the receiver, the institution and the student, to the effect that there are no misunderstandings about the activities and prevent the practitioner.

Evaluation mechanisms linking model are real, systematic and continuing through instruments that do not qualify or disqualify, but that measure the degree to which everyone is involved and each of the actors pairing, from his own experience. Assess relevance, benefits and results. Evaluations should be the beginning, middle and at the end of the cycle.

Generic models and propose practical training tools in each of the various exit profiles in the area of tourism, which go from the planning, operation, systematization, monitoring and evaluation, so coordination with the curriculum of the academic program and potential products. Develop internship program from curriculum map for graduate profile of each degree.

Now in the case of meeting the stated objective, it is necessary to design a strategy that defines how to approach to tourism businesses or organizations in the sector, argumentation and justification of professional practices, as well as the content and regulatory conditions of the agreements between the Department of Tourism, Recreation

and Service, through the Coordination of Extension of the University Center for Economic and Administrative Sciences (CUCEA) of the University of Guadalajara and the recipient institutions.

Currently at CUCEA, we have an agreement to do an internship with companies and organizations, but it seems that is not enough because the PP (professional practice) coordinator at CUCEA sends the students to the companies to do their PP but they do not do a specific evaluation or monitoring the process.

It seems that we have much work to do, not only to fulfill the new curricula, but also to make sure that students have to be ready for the “real world”, this mean, what the companies need, and have to be integrally.

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